

XYLELLA FASTIDIOSA SUBSP. *FASTIDIOSA* DETECTED ON SWEET CHERRY TREES IN MALLORCA, SPAIN

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Following the identification in 2013 of *Xylella fastidiosa* in the southern of Italy, rapid emergency measures have been implemented in the EU for its prevention, detection and surveillance. In the framework of routine inspections performed in Mallorca, Spain, in October 2016, samples were taken from an open air nursery, and some sweet cherry plants were analyzed according to the protocol of the European and Mediterranean Plant Protection Organization (EPPO, 2016) and found positives for *X. fastidiosa* by two real time PCR tests. Besides, the bacteria was isolated in two media after 11 days of incubation. The MLST analysis of genes *leuA*, *petC*, *malF*, *cysG*, *holC*, *nuoL* and *glT* identified the isolate as *X. fastidiosa* subsp. *fastidiosa*.

ST-1. Subsequent sampling in the same nursery allowed the identification of two other cherry plants infected by the same bacterium. The cherry plants were grown in the nursery of Mallorca for the last four years and did not show typical leaf scorch symptoms. They were previously cultivated in another nursery in Tarragona (Spain) that imported them from The Netherlands. After confirmation of the analysis, the plants were destroyed right away as required by the EU legislation. The contingency plan of the Spanish Ministry of Agriculture (MAPAMA) was implemented and survey on potential host plants as well as sampling and testing within a radius of 100 m were performed around the infected plants and a buffer zone of 10 km, was designed. This is the second report of *X. fastidiosa* subsp. *fastidiosa* in an EU country after the detection of this subspecies in an oleander plant in Germany.